

Conceptual photography and the Philippine society: A visual story telling

Mervin G. Sanding*

School of Business and Computer Studies, St. Dominic College of Asia

*Corresponding author: mgsanding@sdca.edu.ph

Abstract

The research aims to create a photographic visual storytelling that gives awareness about the social issues and problems our country has been facing to this moment with the integration of Augmented Reality (AR) that students could use to learn and value the fundamentals in principle and element of design. The researchers used a quantitative method to determine numerical data and percentages according to the relationship between the population of the students from different schools and the effectivity of the creative output. The study revealed that a large part of the population answered that their lack of awareness regarding these issues came from absorbing unreliable information. Thus, the creation of the Augmented Reality (AR) provides a different type of learning and in a creative style. According to the respondents of this study, the aesthetic and quality of the output is rated as 'Very Good' and gives out a positive effect on the overall output which is based on the Likert scale. Regarding the functionality and quality of the output, both are also rated as 'Very Good'. It is therefore recommended and proved by the researchers that the creation of these research gives a creative and a more reliable source that would further show examples of principle and elements of design.

Keywords: Digital, augmented reality, conceptual photography.

To cite this article:

Sanding, M. G. (2021). Conceptual photography and the Philippine society: A visual story telling. *MMA Research Journal*, 2, 6-14.

Introduction

“*Noli Me Tangere*” or Touch Me Not and “*El Filibusterismo*” a masterpiece created by the Philippines’ National Hero, Dr. Jose Rizal, has the underlying message of how the Philippines suffer from a social cancer due to the colonizers—the Spaniards. The protagonist of the said novel, Crisostomo Ibarra, was carrying the burden of setting his country free from the reign of the tyrant Spaniards. The novels show the corruption and mistreatment of the Filipinos on their own land, the state of the depressive society he moves in. The novels he wrote was the reflection of what was the standing of the Philippines then.

But then as the saga of fighting for our freedom and sovereignty took place and then was finally claimed, in the span of hundreds of years, it seems as if a new problem is what we face today. The article mentions one of the many political problem(s) of the Philippines. Especially now with the invention of technology – opening doors to new social issues (Cabañes, 2017; Kislinger & Kotschal, 2021).

Cyberbullying, phishing, frauds, identity, theft, cyber criminals—the birth of technology, indeed has given humanity an easy access to connecting. The rise of social media and its various platforms that the world now consumes; Facebook, Snapchat, Twitter, and Skype to name a few. One platform, namely, Augmented Reality (AR) is now famous in the new generation. Applications such as Pokemon Go, Snapchat, Facebook, and Tiktok are classified under it. Unlike virtual reality, which creates a completely fictional environment, augmented reality is defined as the real-time integration of digital information with the user's environment. Social issues continue to blow, but it seems as if on the eyes of the new generation, it is invisible. With the effortless access to information, the ‘Generation Z’ seems to be at lost to the society they are moving in – unaware.

A social issue, also known as a social problem, is a situation that certain members of the community consider to be undesirable. Some social issues, such as homicides and traffic deaths due to driving under the influence (DUI), as well as extrajudicial killings, LGBTQ, high crime rate, among others are universally acknowledged; to find solutions before it reaches a point of no return, seeing them in a new spectrum is a way of addressing them. It could be said that without awareness of the issues, one cannot see the mentioned issues on a new spectrum. And even if one is aware, several factors that affect the credibility of the information might confuse the receiver, thus, allowing room for misunderstandings regarding the environment they are in.

The invention of various media platforms and the Filipino’s means of using them—specifically Augmented Reality (AR) is also a reflection of one of the many social issues in the Philippines are under. Applications that ‘enhances’ beauty, hides this and that placed on your face, editing apps that gives a more crispy and melodic voice, games with stunning graphics combined with real places in Manila—the misuse of social media, lack of credible resources and other external factors, they all contribute to the new generation’s insufficient knowledge in the current problems of the society (Ozanne et al., 2013). Thus, little to no solution(s) is granted.

Social problems and society

People in general are supposed to live together in organized groups with shared rules, traditions, and values, and this is how society is described. Individuals are the necessity for a society to be formed, their interaction gives birth to groups and the relationship of that group leads to society. It is simply defined by sociologists as a group of people who share a shared territory and interaction and have a common culture. The word itself has been derived from the Latin word “socius”, meaning “association” or “companionship”. Thus, it could be said that a society is a group of individuals who are associative with each other—having a set of likeness or differences.

Social problems, in accordance to Oxford Dictionary of Sociology (1994), is a broad term that refers to a variety of conditions and abnormal behaviors that arise from social disorganization. It is a generic term that encompasses a variety of diseases and abnormal behaviors that are indications of social disorder. It is a social condition that most people in a society oppose and seek to change through social engineering or social planning. It is a person's resentment at a state of dissatisfaction. When it is detested by a considerable number of people, however, it becomes a social issue.

Thus, not all problems are social unless unsatisfied individuals gather one another, vocalize their displeasure, and join to find a solution. When a problem is shared with others, it becomes social, and one person's activity stimulates others to do the same (Kubrin, 2009). On the other hand, social problems, according to Kallen et al. (1989), are those that are manifested in conditions such as socially produced inequities in money, rights, or education, as well as the developing chaos of our main cities. Social difficulties include crime, juvenile delinquency, mental health care, sexual deviance, and other connected effects of these conditions. However, there is no societal problem if events are not defined as one by society. In other words, if cyberbullying is not seen as a problem by many, then it is not.

A theory proposes that personal problems are linked with the societal problems. Personal issues, according to Mills (1959), are problems that affect individuals and that the affected individual, as well as other members of society, attribute to the individual's own personal and moral flaws. Problems such as eating disorders, divorce, and unemployment are only a few examples. Public issues are societal problems that affect many people and have their origins in a society's social structure and culture. Individual difficulties might thus be explained in terms of societal issues. Mills believed that many difficulties that are typically thought of as personal problems are best understood as public issues, and he developed the phrase sociological imagination to describe the ability to see the structural roots of individual problems. A social problem is a societal issue that makes it difficult for individuals to reach their full potential. Poverty, unemployment, unequal opportunity, racism, and malnutrition are some examples of social problems, and with technology, added terms are coined for the negative actions and or crimes done thru along with the media platforms.

Society, politics, and economy—three aspects thoroughly linked with one another. Solving the major social problems would then create a domino effect to the other two the social problems. That includes extrajudicial killings, LGBTQ, and high crime rate not just in the real world but also in the cyber world. To find solutions before it reaches a point of no return, seeing them in a new spectrum is a way of addressing them.

Relevance of Augmented Reality to Education

To improve the user experience, augmented reality puts virtual, computer-generated augmentations onto the real world (Bullock, 2018). This might get you confused with virtual reality, but really it is both different in some ways. As for its educational purposes, it serves as a help for students, and it is an effective learning process in remembering and acquiring contents presented to them.

Augmented reality is taking over every popular social media in the world, whether it may be from certain games that somehow simulates you into their world or using virtual dog filters for fun with your friends (Dani, 2018). It has made a mark in the modern world where technologies are thriving. To add on to that, augmented reality is now also used to elevate your way in giving awareness. It helps you distribute messages through a more innovative way. This can take you to a much wider audience because of its unusual type of engaging information into their minds.

Social Awareness Through Arts

According to Sudhakar (2017), art serves as a valuable tool for social reform in addition to providing a space for aesthetic expression. Artists are given the freedom to express themselves in any way they want. They have a great deal of power when it comes to engaging the public and spreading social ideas. Visual art is important for communicating ideas to an audience since it appeals to people on a sensual level while also driving home a social agenda in a tasteful manner. Art has always been fundamental to any movement that aimed to transform a social setting to improve humanity's intellectual development.

Art has been very influential for many years now. It has been a way of portraying and communicating messages through time. Art, in many ways has been especially useful in conveying messages to the society—a great example of this is promoting social awareness to everybody. Visual arts have been the best way to transmit social changes through the years. It has been widely used to educate everybody about the social issues and how to approach it. Many paintings were created throughout the Renaissance period to honor the perfection and infallibility of human achievement. Now, art can be portrayed in a lot of ways: Photography, Filmmaking, Drawing, Architecture, and Sculpting. This only proves that art comes from way back our history, and it has been part of it for every period, and it will still be in the future.

Color Relation to Psychology

The study of colors in connection to human behavior is known as color psychology. Its goal is to figure out how color influences a person's day-to-day decisions (Cherry, 2020). Colors affect one person's moods and influence their perceptions. As Isaac Newton, an English scientist, discovered that pure white light splits into all the visible colors when it passes through a prism, he also discovered that each color is made up of a single wavelength that cannot be separated further into other colors. There are little theoretical or empirical work regarding the influence of color to psychological functioning, but despite of that, the concept of color psychology became very common especially in terms of marketing, advertising, arts, and design.

Perceptions of colors might be subjective, but there are certain colors that have universal meanings. Warm colors such as red, orange, and yellow create emotions ranging from sentiments of warmth and comfort to feelings of rage and hatred. Cool colors like blue, purple, and green are typically described as soothing, yet they can also evoke feelings of despair or apathy. Though colors have certain meanings, it is still unknown to why or how colors influence people's perception and behavior. According to Crowley (1993), color produces two reactions: arousal reaction and evaluative reaction. Arousal in physiological state means increases in blood pressure, and rate of respiration, high adrenaline, in psychology, it means active and alertness. Exposing to warm colors such as red creates arousal reaction, which is why the color of sale banner is red, because red color is the most physiological at psychological activating color among others. In evaluative reaction, cool colors especially blue are more preferred than warm colors because according to studies, blue has the strong evaluative appeal. That is why people mostly preferred blue over red. Color produces an evaluative reaction because it involves associative network on the brain. When a person sees a color blue, it sees sky and sea and the feeling of calmness because blue associates to those things (Elliot et al., 2015).

Statement of the Problem

The research aims to create the photographic visual storytelling of Philippine society that students enlighten and draw them to the relevant issues in the society. This study would immerse the respondents' consciousness and be an active part of the society.

The study aims to answer these following questions:

1. What are the factors that affect the lack of awareness of the “Generation Z” on the current social issues in the Philippine Society?
2. What are the features of the photographic visual story that would educate the viewers?
3. What is the respondents' evaluation with the photographic visual storytelling in terms of?
 - 3.1. Aesthetics
 - 3.2. Quality
 - 3.3. Functionality

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. The integration of conceptual photography with color theory and multimedia learning enhancement

As shown in figure 1, the conceptual photography is the initial phase. To attain infusion on emotional element into the vision, application of the color psychology is necessary because it influences moods and perceptions to human. Once color is applied to the conceptual photography, the use of the augmented reality amplifies the experience as it creates experience that is more concrete for the audience.

Figure 2 presents the design and plan for the study. The framework serves as guide in developing the output. In the input phase, gathering of vital information and data, conceptual photography and software requirements are planned out. The next phase is process phase, continued with the development of the conceptual photography and the application of Augmented Reality. The output phase is the prototype which will be implemented and evaluated by the respondents. With the evaluations and recommendations being added, the output will be improved based on the data collected.

Figure 2. IPO of the study

Methodology

Research Design

In this study, the formation of the photographic visual storytelling of Philippine society involves a quantitative method. The proponent utilized this method to gather numerical data from questionnaires to the respondents and quantify this to determine the essential elements and components which were added in the design concept. This affected the proponents with their creation of the design, considering the results coming from the questionnaires.

This study was classified to be descriptive research due to its nature of studying characteristics of a population corresponding to the lack of awareness with social issues. The purpose of the study is to assure that the current generation; specifically, the Generation Z will be a vital participant in the society by spreading awareness with the Philippine society.

Population, Sample Size, and Sampling Technique

The respondents of this study are composed of thirty (30) students from different school that the researchers will choose using random sampling technique. Selection would be depending on the participants' availability.

Description of the Respondents

The respondents of the study should be those under “Generation Z” or people that are born from 1995 to 2012 (Diaz, 2017). The respondents would be composed of thirty (30) students, age range from 16 to 20 years old. Respondents may be male or female.

Research Instrument

A survey questionnaire was distributed as a 5-point Likert scale type questionnaire towards the respondents. The quantitative responses for the questionnaire include a forced choice five (5)-

point Likert scale composed of strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, and strongly disagree. The research conductors validated the survey instrument themselves.

Table 1. Rating scale criteria

Rating	Remarks
4.50 – 5.00	Poor
3.50 – 4.49	Fair
2.50 – 3.49	Good
1.50 – 2.49	Very Good
1.00 – 1.49	Excellent

The remarks were based on the following criteria:

- Aesthetic.** Visual elements of the output
- Functionality.** The usefulness of the output
- Quality.** Overall feel and efficiency of the output.

Data Gathering Procedure

From the selected population of the respondents and the research instruments, the source of data was derived from the questionnaires to be given towards the Generation Z students. The participating respondents will be randomly chosen based on their availability and accessibility. The students would then test out the photographic visual storytelling output and will rate on the questionnaire based on their experience with the study.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The statistical tools applied to interpret the data include the average arithmetic mean and the percentage. The average arithmetic mean was used to find out the average of the responses in five (5) options, namely (5) poor, (4) fair, (3) good, (2) very good, (1) excellent which was used to rate the acceptability of the prototype. On the other hand, the percentage was used by the researcher in treating the profiles of the respondents.

Results and Discussion

1. Factors that affect the lack of awareness of the ‘Generation Z’ on current social issues

The results based on the respondents’ evaluation on what factors that affect the lack of awareness of the ‘Generation Z’ on current social issues. Respondents were able to choose multiple options on the questionnaire thus the total numbers of responses exceed the number of respondents. Based on the percentage indicated, 33.33% of the respondents believe misuse of social media platforms, 76.66% perceived abundant false or incorrect news or information, 20% of respondents think of the lack of resources, and 3.33% or one (1) respondent voted for others.

2. Features of the visual story that would educate the viewers

The results from the respondents’ evaluation regarding on what features of the visual story that would educate the viewers. Respondents were able to choose multiple options on the questionnaire thus the total numbers of responses exceed the number of respondents. As referred

on the respondents' answers, 30% or nine (9) votes recognized a realistic visual story, 43.33% or thirteen (13) votes preferred creativity of the visual story, and 46.66% or fourteen (14) votes from the respondents favored the relatable aspect of the visual story.

3. Respondents' evaluation on the photographic visual storytelling

Aesthetics refers to the design appeal of the prototype whether the design served its functionality. Based on the result of the arithmetic mean; the two indicators gained 2.4 for the strong application of contrast and shadows, and 2.5 for the applied color enhancement for visual perception, which is interpreted as 'Very Good.'

Quality refers to the durability of the materials used to build the dual graphics equipment. The prototype was evaluated as 'Very Good' in terms of its quality appeal as indicated by the mean rating of 1.9 for "Invokes emotion through visual perception."

Functionality is measured as the capability of the project serve its purpose for which it was designed. It determines the project's usefulness and performance to the end user. Based on the results presented, the prototype garnered a 2.06 on being able to communicate with the viewer with the social issues, and 2.4 on being able to promote original Filipino artworks, with a 2.23 average mean, it can be interpreted as Very Good.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Consisting of the highest percentage in the results, it could be concluded that the lack of reliable information that could educate the Generation Y, is the hindrance for their awareness. The misuse of the social media platforms available is another factor to be considered, given the fact that most information that shapes the perception of today's generation.

Based on the highest percentage gathered in the survey, saying that the creativity of the prototype helped to send the message of awareness. It catches the attention of its viewers and at the same time, informs. The relatable and realistic aspect adds more mark on the prototype.

According to the aesthetics of the visual story, the survey results showed positive remark on the contrast and shadows, as well as the color enhancement. The Generation Y acknowledged the efforts of the researchers on the prototype and found it pleasing.

Likewise, quality takes place for the prototype. The proponents concluded that invoking of emotions in the respondents using the prototype is essential, with its high rate, concluding that it is effectively agreeable.

Based on the conducted AR presentation, the proponents found that the AR presentation and the creative output caught the attention of the respondents and awakened awareness in them. The presentation attains its purpose—to raise awareness and inform the Generation Y of the current social issues the Philippines is suffering from.

Listed are the recommendations suggested by the researchers for the awareness of the Generation Z, and not just them, but for others too. This study will provide creative outputs accompanied by a video explaining the social issues chosen that could be presented in but is not limited to schools. Teachers and professors will benefit from the result of this study because they can use augmented reality and the prototypes as an effective way of teaching social issues. Schools

and universities will also benefit from using augmented reality in their area of advertising. The study will provide relevant information as a reference for future studies on merging art and technology.

References

- Bullock, L. (2018, November 16). *AR And social media: Is augmented reality the future of social media?* Forbes. <https://www.forbes.com/sites/lilachbullock/2018/11/16/ar-and-social-media-is-augmented-reality-the-future-of-social-media/?sh=343e6e0de141>
- Cabañes, J. V. A. (2017). Migrant narratives as photo stories: On the properties of photography and the mediation of migrant voices. *Visual Studies*, 32(1), 33-46. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1472586X.2016.1245114>
- Cherry, K. (2020, May 28). *Color psychology: Does it affect how you feel? How colors impact moods, feelings, and behaviors.* Verywellmind. <https://www.verywellmind.com/color-psychology-2795824>
- Crowley, A. E. (1993). The two-dimensional impact of color on shopping. *Marketing Letters*, 4(1), 59-69. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00994188>
- Dani, V. (2018, February 28). *5 reasons to use augmented reality in education.* Kitaboo. <https://kitaboo.com/5-reasons-use-augmented-reality-education/>
- Diaz, A. (2017, September 21). *The age of zentennials: How to raise Gen Z? Awesome!* <https://awesome.blog/2017/09/raising-gen-z-the-zentennial-generation.html>
- Elliot, A. J., Fairchild, M. D., & Franklin, A. (Eds.). (2015). *Handbook of color psychology.* Cambridge University Press.
- Kallen, D. J., Miller, D., & Daniels, A. (1989). Sociology, social work and social problems. *Sociological Practice*, 7(1), 97-109.
- Kislinger, L., & Kotschal, K. (2021). Hunters and gatherers of pictures: Why photography has become a human universal. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 654474. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.654474>
- Kubrin, C. E. (2009). Social disorganization theory: Then, now, and in the future. In M. D. Krohn, A. J. Lizotte, & G. P. Hall (Eds.), *Handbook on crime and deviance* (pp. 225-236). Springer Science+Business Media. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-0245-0_12
- Ozanne, J. L., Moscato, E. M., & Kunkel, D. R. (2013). Transformative photography: Evaluation and best practices for eliciting social and policy changes. *Journal of Public Policy & Marketing*, 32(1), 45-65. <https://doi.org/10.1509/jppm.11.161>
- Sudhakar, S. (2017, November 21). *The art in social awareness.* University Observer. <https://universityobserver.ie/the-art-in-social-awareness/>